

Provenance Guidelines for Workflow and Tool Developers

To ensure the provenance tracking, reproducibility, and transparency of bioinformatics workflows and tools, we have established these guidelines for developers. These guidelines encompass critical aspects such as detailed documentation, version management, data handling, and validation practices. By adhering to these standards, developers can ensure that their workflows are not only scientifically sound but also easily reproducible and verifiable.

There are 5 sections:

- (1) Improve Reproducibility
- (2) Version Report (output file: versions.yml)
- (3) Data and Metadata Management (output file: provenance.yml)
- (4) Documentation
- (5) Validation, Cooperation and Sharing

Moreover, to facilitate continuous improvement and accountability, we introduce a scoring system. This system evaluates each workflow based on its compliance with the outlined guidelines, assigning a rating that reflects its adherence to best practices. This rating system serves as a benchmark for quality, helping developers identify areas for enhancement and providing users with a reliable measure of a workflow's reliability and reproducibility. The highest score is 100 provenance points.

(1) Improve Reproducibility (20 points)

Pin All Versions:

- Ensure that all software versions used in the workflow are explicitly pinned.
- The use of the ' :latest ' tag is not allowed to maintain reproducibility.

Random Seed Fixing:

- Where applicable, fix random seeds (e.g. using `set.seed(42)` for R or `random.seed(42)` for python).

(2) Semantic Version Report (20 points)

Generate versions.yml (for workflows):

- On each execution, the workflow generates a `versions.yml` file compliant with nf-core standards.
- This file should contain the versions of all software used in the pipeline.

- Ensure that the `versions.yml` file is included in the list of output files emitted by the workflow.
- This file should be readily accessible for users to verify the software versions used in the workflow execution.
- Use the following template to create the `versions.yml` file (nf workflow):

```
1 cat <<-END_VERSIONS >versions.yml
2 "${task.process}":
3 proteinotho: \$(echo \$(proteinotho --version 2>&1) )
4 BLAST: \$(echo \$(blastp -v 2>&1) )
5 ...
6 END_VERSIONS
```

For example: <https://gitlab.uni-marburg.de/synmikro/ag-lechner/proteinotho-nf>
(main.nf)

Generate provenance file (for tools):

- On each execution, generate a file containing the current version of the tool called `<TOOLNAME>.info`
- Use the following template to create the `versions.yml` file (nf workflow):

```
1 cat <<-END_VERSIONS >proteinotho.info
2 proteinotho: \$(echo \$(proteinotho --version 2>&1) )
3 END_VERSIONS
```

(3) Data and Metadata Management (20 points)

On each execution, the workflow generates a file e.g. called `provenance.yml` that reports:

Metadata Collection:

- Capture and store the metadata related to each workflow/tool run, including:
 - Date and time of execution
 - User or system initiating the workflow
 - All parameters and flags
 - Computational environment (e.g., operating system)

Input Data:

- Maintain a record of all input data files, including their source, format, checksum (md5).

Intermediate Data:

- Document intermediate data files generated during workflow execution.
- Ensure that intermediate data can be traced back to specific steps in the workflow.

Output Data:

- Provide clear descriptions and formats for output files.

The Provenance Report `provenance.yml`:

- The `provenance.yml` file should have the following form:

```
system:
  execution-start: 1721347650
  execution-end: 1721347981
  user: paul
  os: ubuntu 20.04, focal-20240530
parameters:
  conn: 20
  ev: 1e-5
  cpus: 20
cmd: proteinortho.pl -conn=20 -ev=1e-5 -cpus=20 file1.faa ...
input:
  file1.faa:
    md5:16f6e2deeb83ec5c1c075e052c8f187c
  ...
intermediate:
  myproject_tmp/res.out:
    step:the intermediate results of the all-versus-all blasting
    md5:16f6e2deeb83ec5c1c075e052c8f187c
  ...
result:
  myproject.blast-graph:
    description:pairwise reciprocal best hit table (tsv)
    md5:16f6e2deeb83ec5c1c075e052c8f187c
  ...
```

For example, see the `main.nf` of

<https://gitlab.uni-marburg.de/synmikro/ag-lechner/proteinortho-nf>

(4) Documentation (20 points)

Detailed Documentation:

- Provide comprehensive documentation for the workflow/tool, including instructions for installation, configuration, and execution.
- Include explanations for each step in the workflow and the purpose of each tool or software used as well as the parameters.
- Provide example data and instruction to execute.
- Acceptable platforms are: readthedocs, GitHub Wiki, Readme.md

(5) Validation, Collaboration and Sharing (20 points)

Tests:

- Implement tests (e.g. using gitlab ci or github ci) to validate your workflow automatically on change / update.
- Ensure that changes to the workflow are reviewed and tested before publishing.

Collaboration:

- Use version control systems (e.g., Git) for collaborative development.
- Encourage user feedback and contributions to improve the workflow.

Specific implementation advise for nextflow with RO-Crate

The Developer is advised to use the RO-Crate standard to bundle outputs, inputs, and metadata into a FAIR-compliant research object. This can be done in a dedicated nextflow process (e.g. called GENERATE_RO_CRATE):

1. Installing RO-Crate (Python)
2. Packing metadata with rocrate command

```
1. rocrate init
2. rocrate add file <filename> -P name=<logical name> -P description=<desc> -P
   md5=<checksum>
3. rocrate add file versions.yml -P name=versions -P
   description="versions" -P md5=\$(md5sum versions.yml |
   awk '{print \$1}') ...
4. rocrate add workflow -l nextflow main.nf
```

Required Files:

- Input files (with checksums and descriptions)
- Output and intermediate files (with logical names and checksums)
- versions.yml (from section 2)
- provenance.yml (from section 3)
- Workflow script (e.g., main.nf)

RO-Crate Output Location:

The crate metadata (ro-crate-metadata.json) should be included as an emitted output file and published for downstream FAIR sharing.

Optional:

- Consider signing the RO-Crate or including DOI references to referenced tools.
- Use runcrate to convert the ro-crate object to a provenance run crate object
`runcrate convert --profile provenance_run_crate --output=ro-crate-prov.json .`